

COLLECTION OF INFORMATION IN THE SYSTEM OF INTERNAL MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION AND ITS PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSIS

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Annotation. *In this article it has been described the notion of collecting, information in the system internal heading of educational establishments and its pedagogical analyses.*

Key words: *analyses, information system, heading, method, education, upbringing, control, administration, degree.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье раскрыт сущность сбор информации в системе внутреннего управления образовательного учреждения и ее педагогический анализ.*

Ключевые слова: *анализ, информация, система, управление, метод, образование, воспитание, контроль, администрация, степень.*

The collection and analysis of information in the internal management system of an educational institution is an important condition and an effective method of management that facilitates the determination of solutions and activities aimed at improving educational and upbringing work.

In fact, the collection and analysis of information is considered an important condition for improving the activities of the educational institution when planning activities both from a scientific and methodological point of view, and from a

pedagogical point of view. The pedagogical significance of the collection and analysis of information in the internal management system of the educational institution is very wide.

For this purpose the links of the continuous education system and the heads of educational institutions should pay special attention to this issue.

The information accumulated in the internal management system of an educational institution can be divided into two groups:

1. Legislative information.
2. Information accumulated by control (information on the state of work).

Decrees and Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the system of continuous education, Decrees and orders of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the system of continuous education, various orders, methodical instructions of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as decisions and instructive and methodological instructions of the college in the system of continuing education are referred to the directive information.

This information is brought to the attention of every teacher, educator and technical workers of the administration and various public organizations of the educational institution. Arming the educational staff of the educational institution with directive information opens up great opportunities for the correct organization and improvement of the teaching and upbringing work of the educational institution, with increasing responsibility of each member of the pedagogical staff for their work. For this reason, the collection of directive information in the system of internal management of an educational institution and its training of the pedagogical collective is of great pedagogical importance.

The main purpose of collecting information for control purposes is to identify the state of practical implementation of instructions, instructive and methodological instructions of the administration of the educational institution, the state of the

educational and upbringing level of students, the issues of improving the pedagogical skills of teachers and educators, their extracurricular work and work outside the educational institution and a number of other issues.

To fulfill the tasks facing the educational institution today, the pedagogical process should make an impact on the managerial activity of the head of the educational institution. For the correct and timely provision of influence, one should be aware of the daily state of this process. The head of an educational institution, like any other leader, can successfully carry out his activities only if he has reliable information, as well as its essence and content regarding educational and upbringing issues.

The head of the educational institution, armed with reliable information on the issues of teaching and upbringing work, will have the opportunity to analyze the expected results, and thereby outline measures to introduce changes in the pedagogical process and improve it.

Thus, the importance and usefulness of decisions and actions taken by the manager in the internal management system of an educational institution depends on the scientific, completeness and reliability of the information received by him. The degree to which the pedagogical process influences the educational process in the management system of the educational institution of the leader is largely determined by the correct organization by them of obtaining complete and reliable information on the state of work and the ability to correctly analyze it.

The information, which is directly related to the issues of the educational and material and technical base, teaching and upbringing work, extra-curricular activities and work of the out-of-school institution, pedagogical workers, as well as the financial and economic activities of the educational institution, are divided into three main types:

1. Written information.
2. Oral information.
3. Statistical information.

This information is the instructive instructions approved by the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, calculated for a certain period (weekly, monthly, quarterly, semi-annual and annual) is accumulated, summarized and sent to the relevant parts of the education system. To do this, it is important that the head of the educational institution and his deputies must determine in advance the topics and sources of information.

We considered it expedient to indicate below the sources of this information:

1. Indicators of the national economy plan of the educational institution.
2. The activities of the educational institution in the implementation of general compulsory education.
3. The activity of the educational institution on the issues of educational-material and technical base.
4. Educational and educational work.
5. Extra-curricular work and work of an out-of-school institution.
6. The work of the information and resource center of the educational institution.
7. The activities of the educational institution in cooperation with families and the public.
8. The activities of the educational institution in cooperation with sponsored and production organizations.
9. The activities of the educational institution in cooperation with educational institutions on the scale of the district (city).
10. The activity of an educational institution in cooperation with urban or rural professional colleges.
11. The activity of the educational institution in cooperation with higher educational institutions.

12. Record keeping in an educational institution.

13. Financial and economic activity of the educational institution.

14. Work to provide students with hot food and tea (buffet and canteen educational institution).

15. Activities of the educational institution associated with the parent committee.

16. Agitation activities of the educational institution on the issue of education and upbringing.

17. Work on the organization of medical services for students.

18. Work on the organization of vehicles for students of an educational institution.

19. Work to improve the skills and retraining of teachers.

20. Activities of the educational council of the educational institution and other issues.

This source is in turn considered an internal source of the educational institution. From each given source, you can collect information on various issues based on a specific topic. Therefore, it is important that the head of each educational institution in the distribution of responsibilities among managers should develop in advance the topic of information and collect them within the prescribed time limit.

The degree of leadership of the head of the educational institution depends on the purposeful and timely collection of reliable information on the activities of each teacher, the quality of students' knowledge, their level of upbringing and discipline. An important means of collecting this kind of information is to exercise internal control of the educational institution by determining the state of educational work, which is, monitoring the lessons of teachers.

The pedagogical and general cultural potential of the teacher, the level of his knowledge and preparedness for the lesson, the expedient organization of mental work for students, the process of gaining knowledge of them can all be determined

only by observing the lesson. Or, in other words, information on this issue can be collected by observing the lesson.

Another way to collect information about the state of teaching and upbringing work is to talk with teachers and students, get acquainted with the written documentation of the teacher (work plan, methodological developments, notes in class journals), daybooks, writing and other types of student work, use of statistical data, Pedagogical analysis, questioning of students and others. A great pedagogical significance is the operative analysis of the collected information on the result of the educational work. In this case, it is necessary to indicate not only errors and omissions, but also comprehensively identify the causes of their occurrence.

This, in the first place, should be remembered especially when checking the quality of students' knowledge. Based on observations of lessons and findings on the results of the analysis of the information received on the level of knowledge of students, the number of assignments made and other relevant parameters to the leaders of educational institutions should outline urgent measures to improve the teaching and upbringing process. Since if every information is analyzed and no measures are taken on the basis of these analyzes to improve performance, then it should not be expected that such information collection and analysis will benefit. Therefore, the head of each educational institution should not leave this issue outside its field of vision.

After acquaintance with this information, the heads of educational institutions conduct an operative pedagogical analysis of these data, outline plans for improving the pedagogical activity of teachers and class leaders, and introduce them into the life of the educational institution in one form or another. Such internal management increases the effectiveness of the educational and upbringing activities of the educational institution.

The head of an educational institution is the only responsible state for the whole organization and quality of the educational and upbringing activity of the educational

institution. The organizational activity of the head of the educational institution is multifaceted. He should guide the work of teachers, class leaders, manage financial and economic activities, know all the subtleties of this activity, and manage extracurricular work and the work of an out-of-school institution.

The head of the educational institution is very difficult to solve all urgent problems without his close associates. Therefore, when forming the younger generation, his assistants should give correct instructions to teachers, provide them with practical help, and keep an eye on the process of their activities.

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